

Earth Systems and Environment

Integrating Expert Knowledge and Fuzzy Logic for Landslide Susceptibility Mapping: A Case Study of Mindoro Island, Philippines

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Weight Estimates for the Twelve Landslide-Conditioning Variables Used in the Fuzzy Weighted Function

Variable	Weight	References
Annual Rainfall	7.39%	Ali et al., 2021; Badola et al., 2023; Barrile et al., 2016; Dong et al., 2024; Dou et al., 2023; Fayez et al., 2018; Feizizadeh et al., 2014; Gheshlaghi and Feizizadeh, 2017; Hong et al., 2017; Kab et al., 2023; Klai et al., 2024; Leonardi et al., 2016; Mengstie et al., 2024; Nsengiyumva and Valentino, 2020; Nwazelibe et al., 2023; Pham et al., 2021; Razavi-Termeh et al., 2023; Roy and Saha, 2019; Sur et al., 2020; Vakhshoori and Zare, 2016; Wang et al., 2024
Elevation	11.27%	Akgun et al., 2012; Ali et al., 2021; Barrile et al., 2016; Chang et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2017; Devara et al., 2021; Dong et al., 2024; Fayez et al., 2018; Gaidzik et al., 2017; Gheshlaghi and Feizizadeh, 2017; Gorsevski and Jankowski, 2010; Hong et al., 2017, 2018; Huang et al., 2018, 2025; Ilanloo, 2011; Jaafari et al., 2019; Kab et al., 2023; Leonardi et al., 2016; Nsengiyumva and Valentino, 2020; Nwazelibe et al., 2023; Oh and Pradhan, 2011; Pham et al., 2021; Roy and Saha, 2019; Saygin et al., 2023; Sezer et al., 2011; Sur et al., 2020; Tella et al., 2025; Vakhshoori and Zare, 2016; Wang et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024; Zheng and Ding, 2024
Land Cover and Land Use	11.62%	Alcântara et al., 2024; Ali et al., 2021; Barrile et al., 2016; Bui et al., 2012, 2015; Chen et al., 2017; Devara et al., 2021; Dong et al., 2024; Dou et al., 2023; Fayez et al., 2018; Feizizadeh et al., 2014; Gheshlaghi and Feizizadeh, 2017; Ilanloo, 2011; Jaafari et al., 2019; Kab et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2019; Klai et al., 2024; Leonardi et al., 2016; Mengstie et al., 2024; Nsengiyumva and Valentino, 2020; Nwazelibe et al., 2023; Oliveira et al., 2024; Panahi et al., 2020; Pham et al., 2021; Razavi-Termeh et al., 2023; Roy and Saha, 2019; Saygin et al., 2023; Sezer et al., 2011; Sur et al., 2020; Tella et al., 2025; Vahidnia et al., 2010; Vakhshoori and Zare, 2016; Wang et al., 2024
Fault Distance	9.86%	Ali et al., 2021; Bui et al., 2012, 2015; Chen et al., 2017; Dong et al., 2024; Dou et al., 2023; Feizizadeh et al., 2014; Gheshlaghi and Feizizadeh, 2017; Hong et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2025; Ilanloo, 2011; Jaafari et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2019; Klai et al., 2024; Mengstie et al., 2024; Nsengiyumva and Valentino, 2020; Oh and Lee, 2011; Pham et al., 2021; Razavi-Termeh et al., 2023; Roy and Saha, 2019; Sezer et al., 2011; Sur et al., 2020; Tella et al., 2025; Vahidnia et al., 2010; Vakhshoori and Zare, 2016; Wang et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024; Zheng and Ding, 2024

Variable	Weight	References
Road Distance	8.80%	Ali et al., 2021; Bui et al., 2012; Chang et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2017; Dong et al., 2024; Dou et al., 2023; Fayez et al., 2018; Feizizadeh et al., 2014; Gheshlaghi and Feizizadeh, 2017; Hong et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2025; Ilanloo, 2011; Jaafari et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2019; Mengstie et al., 2024; Nsengiyumva and Valentino, 2020; Oh and Pradhan, 2011; Pham et al., 2021; Razavi-Termeh et al., 2023; Roy and Saha, 2019; Sur et al., 2020; Tella et al., 2025; Vakhshoori and Zare, 2016; Wang et al., 2024; Zheng and Ding, 2024
River Distance	11.97%	Ali et al., 2021; Bui et al., 2012; Chang et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2017; Dong et al., 2024; Dou et al., 2023; Fayez et al., 2018; Feizizadeh et al., 2014; Gaidzik et al., 2017; Gheshlaghi and Feizizadeh, 2017; Gupta et al., 2018; Hong et al., 2017, 2018; Huang et al., 2018, 2025; Ilanloo, 2011; Jaafari et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2019; Klai et al., 2024; Mengstie et al., 2024; Nsengiyumva and Valentino, 2020; Oh and Pradhan, 2011; Oleng et al., 2024; Pham et al., 2021; Razavi-Termeh et al., 2023; Roy and Saha, 2019; Sezer et al., 2011; Sur et al., 2020; Tella et al., 2025; Vahidnia et al., 2010; Vakhshoori and Zare, 2016; Wang et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024; Zheng and Ding, 2024
Slope	17.25%	Akgun et al., 2012; Aksoy and Ercanoglu, 2012; Alcântara et al., 2024; Ali et al., 2021; Badola et al., 2023; Barrile et al., 2016; Bui et al., 2012, 2015; Chang et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2017; Devara et al., 2021; Dong et al., 2024; Dou et al., 2023; Fayez et al., 2018; Feizizadeh et al., 2014; Gaidzik et al., 2017; Gheshlaghi and Feizizadeh, 2017; Gorsevski and Jankowski, 2010; Gupta et al., 2018; Hong et al., 2017, 2018; Huang et al., 2018, 2025; Ilanloo, 2011; Jaafari et al., 2019; Kab et al., 2023; Khan et al., 2019; Klai et al., 2024; Leonardi et al., 2016; Mengstie et al., 2024; Nsengiyumva and Valentino, 2020; Nwazelibe et al., 2023; Oh and Pradhan, 2011; Oleng et al., 2024; Oliveira et al., 2024; Panahi et al., 2020; Pham et al., 2021; Razavi-Termeh et al., 2023; Roy and Saha, 2019; Saygin et al., 2023; Sezer et al., 2011; Sur et al., 2020; Tella et al., 2025; Vahidnia et al., 2010; Vakhshoori and Zare, 2016; Wang et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024; Zheng and Ding, 2024; Zhu et al., 2014

Variable	Weight	References
Aspect	13.73%	Ali et al., 2021; Badola et al., 2023; Bui et al., 2012, 2015; Chen et al., 2017; Devara et al., 2021; Dong et al., 2024; Dou et al., 2023; Fayez et al., 2018; Feizizadeh et al., 2014; Gaidzik et al., 2017; Gheshlaghi and Feizizadeh, 2017; Gupta et al., 2018; Hong et al., 2017, 2018; Huang et al., 2018, 2025; Ilanloo, 2011; Jaafari et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2019; Klai et al., 2024; Mengstie et al., 2024; Nsengiyumva and Valentino, 2020; Nwazelibe et al., 2023; Oh and Lee, 2011; Oleng et al., 2024; Oliveira et al., 2024; Panahi et al., 2020; Pham et al., 2021; Razavi-Termeh et al., 2023; Roy and Saha, 2019; Saygin et al., 2023; Sur et al., 2020; Vahidnia et al., 2010; Vakhshoori and Zare, 2016; Wang et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024; Zheng and Ding, 2024; Zhu et al., 2014
Topographic Wetness Index	7.04%	Akgun et al., 2012; Ali et al., 2021; Badola et al., 2023; Chang et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2017; Dou et al., 2023; Gaidzik et al., 2017; Gorsevski and Jankowski, 2010; Hong et al., 2017, 2018; Jaafari et al., 2019; Mengstie et al., 2024; Nsengiyumva and Valentino, 2020; Oh and Lee, 2011; Panahi et al., 2020; Pham et al., 2021; Razavi-Termeh et al., 2023; Roy and Saha, 2019; Sur et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2024
Sand	0.35%	Mengstie et al., 2024
Clay	0.35%	Mengstie et al., 2024
Silt	0.35%	Mengstie et al., 2024

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